

Antimicrobial Stewardship on the Dairy: evaluating an on-farm framework for training farmworkers.

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Supplemental Table 1. Hands-on activity session template for the examination of five different cows. The hands-on examination of the cows was conducted using a checklist that had thirteen main areas of knowledge focused on observations of clinical relevance for diagnosing disease in the cow

Cow	ID	In front				Behind							Exam	
		Appetite	Attitude	Nasal discharge	Cough	Vaginal discharge	Udder	Manure	Cleanliness	Lameness	Rumen fill	BCS	Rectal T°	Hydration status
1														
2														
3														
4														
5														

Appetite: 0 if the cow is eating, there is a gap in the feed in front; 1 if the feed is undisturbed, she is not eating

Attitude: 0 if the cow is interested in the surroundings; 1 if depressed, Indifferent to normal stimulation; 2 if wobbly or trembling

Nasal discharge: 0 if no discharge; 1 if discharge

Cough: 0 if no cough; 1 if cough

Vaginal discharge: 0 if clear vaginal discharge; 1 if purulent or mucopurulent; 2 if foul watery red-brown

Udder: 0 if normal; 1 if inflammation of the udder

Manure: 0 if normal; 1 if loose manure or diarrhea

Cleanliness: 0 if clean - minor splashing; 1 if very dirty

Lameness: 0 if Sound – normal; 1 if moderate lameness; 2 if severe lameness

Rumen fill/abdomen shape: 0 if normal; 1 if tucked in abdomen; 2 if distended

BCS: 0 if normal (2.5 - 4); 2 if very thin (<2.5); 2 if overweight (4-5)

Rectal temperature: write down the rectal temperature

Hydration status: 0 if normal (1 – 2 seconds); 1 if moderate (less 4 seconds); 2 if severe (5-10 seconds)

Supplemental Table 2. The number of answered and not answered variables for the hands-on activity using a 13-point checklist focused on observations of clinical relevance for diagnosing disease in the cow. The total number of answered variables was included in the accuracy analysis.

Variable	Answer		Not answer	
	n	%	n	%
Appetite	108	88.5	14	11.5
Attitude	122	100	0	0.0
Nasal discharge	122	100	0	0.0
Cough	122	100	0	0.0
Vaginal discharge	120	98.4	2	1.6
Udder	120	98.4	2	1.6
Manure	81	66.4	41	33.6
Cleanliness	122	100	0	0.0
Lameness	116	95.1	6	4.9
Rumen fill	82	67.2	40	32.8
Body condition score	122	100	0	0.0
Hydration status	122	100	0	0.0
Total	1359	92.8	105	7.2

Supplemental Table 3. Pre- and post-attitude assessment responses for the 25 participants enrolled in the training program, for the seven questions in which there was a significant change. P-value corresponds to Wilcoxon signed-rank test for paired data

	<i>Q7. Standard health protocols help me choose proper treatments</i>				<i>Q8. Drug labels should be followed according to veterinarian indications</i>				<i>Q10. Rectal temperature should be assessed daily after calving</i>				<i>Q11. Physical appearance is an important/useful indicator of animal health</i>				<i>Q15. Forestripping helps me identify cases of mastitis</i>				<i>Q16. Milk samples for bacteriological culture can help avoid unnecessary use of AM</i>				<i>Q23. Rectal palpation of the uterus after calving helps me identify cows with metritis</i>			
	pre n	post n	pre %	post %	pre n	post n	pre %	post %	pre n	post n	pre %	post %	pre n	post n	pre %	post %	pre n	post n	pre %	post %	pre n	post n	pre %	post %	pre n	post n	pre %	post %
Strongly agree	13	22	52	88	16	22	64	88	11	17	44	68	17	24	68	96	18	24	72	96	14	23	56	92	15	20	60	80
Somewhat agree	6	1	24	4	2	0	8	0	3	3	12	12	2	4	8	4	4	16	1	4	5	2	8	4	16	4	16	
Neither agree nor disagree	3	1	12	4	2	2	8	8	5	2	20	8	2	0	8	0	1	4	0	0	2	0	8	0	5	20	1	4
Somewhat disagree	0	0	0	0	2	0	8	0	1	1	4	4	3	0	12	0	1	4	0	0	2	0	8	0	1	4	0	0
Strongly disagree	3	1	12	4	3	1	12	4	5	2	20	8	1	0	4	0	1	4	0	0	2	0	8	0	0	0	0	0
p-value	0.008				0.035				0.012				0.017				0.034				0.008				0.019			

Supplemental Table 4. Pre- and post-attitude assessment responses for the 25 participants enrolled in the training program, for the six questions in which there was not a significant change. P-value corresponds to Wilcoxon signed-rank test for paired data

	<i>Q5. The overuse of AMS increases the development of resistant bacteria</i>				<i>Q6. I have the ability to use less AMS without harming animal health</i>				<i>Q17. Cows with mild cases of mastitis do not require AM treatment immediately</i>				<i>Q24. Cows that have twins, retained placenta, or dystocia need to be monitored more frequently</i>				<i>Q25. The decision to treat a cow with abnormal discharge depends on additional clinical signs</i>				<i>Q34. Footrot lesions, if untreated, can progress to a more extensive or systemic infection</i>			
	pre		post		pre		post		pre		post		pre		post		pre		post		pre		post	
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%
Strongly agree	13	52	21	84	13	52	19	76	6	24	12	48	18	72	24	96	16	64	24	96	21	84	23	92
Somewhat agree	4	16	1	4	5	20	3	12	8	32	1	4	4	16	1	4	5	20	0	0	2	8	1	4
Neither agree nor disagree	1	4	0	0	2	8	1	4	2	8	2	8	2	8	0	0	1	4	0	0	2	8	0	0
Somewhat disagree	3	12	1	4	2	8	1	4	3	12	1	4	1	4	0	0	2	8	0	0	0	0	0	0
Strongly disagree	4	16	2	8	3	12	1	4	6	24	9	36	0	0	0	0	1	4	1	4	0	0	1	4
p-value	0.060				0.055				0.907				0.177				0.070				0.670			

Supplemental Table 5. Complete list of individual results from the sensitivity and specificity analysis, from the hands-on activity following a 13-point checklist focused on observations of clinical relevance for diagnosing disease in the cow. (Se: sensitivity, Sp: specificity)

worker	state	TP	TN	FP	FN	na	total	Se	Sp
1	CA	10	44	0	6	0	60	0.625	1.000
2	CA	14	41	2	3	0	60	0.824	0.953
3	CA	6	42	0	5	7	60	0.545	1.000
4	CA	12	43	0	0	5	60	1.000	1.000
5	CA	10	50	0	0	0	60	1.000	1.000
6	CA	10	50	0	0	0	60	1.000	1.000
7	CA	10	50	0	0	0	60	1.000	1.000
8	CA	18	42	0	0	0	60	1.000	1.000
9	CA	18	42	0	0	0	60	1.000	1.000
10	CA	18	42	0	0	0	60	1.000	1.000
11	CA	18	42	0	0	0	60	1.000	1.000
12	CA	18	42	0	0	0	60	1.000	1.000
13	OH	0	54	0	5	1	60	0.000	1.000
14	OH	4	42	1	3	10	60	0.571	0.977
15	OH	5	42	1	2	10	60	0.714	0.977
16	OH	6	38	2	1	13	60	0.857	0.950
17	OH	13	33	4	3	7	60	0.813	0.892
18	OH	14	35	2	2	7	60	0.875	0.946
19	OH	15	35	1	1	8	60	0.938	0.972
20	OH	13	35	1	3	8	60	0.813	0.972
21	OH	11	33	0	0	4	48	1.000	1.000
22	OH	11	33	0	0	4	48	1.000	1.000
23	OH	11	33	0	0	4	48	1.000	1.000
24	OH	8	38	0	0	14	60	1.000	1.000
25	OH	11	46	0	0	3	60	1.000	1.000
averages		11.36	41.08	0.56	1.36	4.2	58.56	0.863	0.98557
totals		284	1027	14	34	105	1464		